

S.No.	PARTICIPANT	Gender	Age	PLACE	score (SES)	Socio-economic Status	score (RC)	Religious Commitment	scores (MW)	Mental Well-being	score (CI)	Community Integration
1	Pratima ma'am	F.	30		22	upper-middle class	33	High religious commit.	53	Average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
2	Ritik Raj	M.	19	Delhi	17	upper-middle class	26	moderate religious commit.	45	Average to high wellbeing	32	Moderate community Integration
3	Harshvardhan Bhatt	M.	21	Delhi	13	lower middle class	44	Very High religious commit.	36	Below average wellbeing	50	High community Integration
4	Aayushi	F.	19	Delhi	25	upper-middle class	36	High religious commit.	55	Average to high wellbeing	33	Moderate community Integration
5	_	M.	21	Delhi	18	lower middle class	38	High religious commit.	49	Average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
6	Girja	M.	22	Delhi	8	lower middle class	23	moderate religious commit.	63	Very High wellbeing	38	High community Integration
7	Khushi Chauhan	F.	23	Delhi	27	upper (I)	41	Very High religious commit.	53	Average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
8	Seema Mishra	F.	55	Delhi	27	upper (I)	41	Very High religious commit.	53	Average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
9	Deepak Chaudhary	M.	20	Faridabad	19	upper-middle (II)	42	Very High religious commit.	59	Average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
10	Khushi Mishra	F.	20	Delhi	25	upper-middle (II)	35	High religious commit.	42	Average to high wellbeing	46	High community Integration
11	Insight	M.	27	New Delhi	19	upper-middle (II)	30	High religious commitment	54	Average to high wellbeing	39	High community Integration
12	Vivek Joshi	M.	22	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	37	High religious commitment	57	Average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
13	Vivek Joshi	M.	21	Prayagraj	22	upper-middle (II)	40	Very High religious commitm	46	Average to high wellbeing	49	High community Integration
14	Shreya	F.	20	Delhi	31	High religious commitment	49	Average to high wellbeing	49	Average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
15	Priyanka Rai	F.	38	Jamshedpur	14	lower middle (III)	50	very High religious commitm	70	very High mental Well-being	45	High community Integration
16	Anmol Gole	M.	21	Gurugram	10	upper lower (III)	31	High religious commitment	64	Very High mental well-being	46	High community Integration
17	_	M.	23	Chandauli	13	lower middle (III)	39	High religious commitment	59	Average to high wellbeing	48	High community Integration
18	_	F.	21	Chandauli	10	upper lower (IV)	39	High religious commitment	64	Average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
19	Vidya	M.	25	Prayagraj	7	lower upper (II)	22	moderate religious commitm	32	Below average wellbeing	23	moderate community Integration
20	Ayush Singh Harsh	M.	23	Gorakhpur	16	upper-middle (II)	17	low religious commitment	29	low mental Well-being	29	moderate community Integration
21	Anshul Rawat	M.	18	Delhi	24	upper-middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	53	Average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
22	Rajiv	M.	20	Chandauli	17	upper middle (II)	24	moderate religious commitm	70	very High mental well-being	38	High community Integration
23	Vinay	M.	29	Noida	6	upper lower (IV)	25	moderate religious commitm	38	below average wellbeing	36	High community Integration
24	Vivek Maurya	M.	23	Chandauli	7	upper lower (IV)	10	low religious commitment	64	average to high wellbeing	18	low community Integration
25	Tejsh Kumar Singh	M.	21	New Delhi	14	lower middle (III)	36	High religious commitment	63	average to high wellbeing	46	High community Integration
26	Khushi Kumari	F.	19	west bengal	23	upper middle (II)	16	low religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
27	Virendra Kumar Mish	M.	42	Ayodhya	13	lower middle (III)	41	very High religious commitm	47	average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
28	_	M.	24	Delhi	11	lower middle (III)	43	very High religious commitm	50	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
29	Arpita Kumari	F.	21	Ara, Bihar	12	lower middle (III)	45	very High religious commitm	51	average to high wellbeing	46	High community Integration
30	Dipti	F.	19	Delhi	25	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	45	average to high wellbeing	31	moderate community Integration
31	_	M.	19	Delhi	19	upper-middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	35	below average wellbeing	27	moderate community Integration
32	Reena Yadav	F.	42	Chandauli, UP	17	upper-middle (II)	41	very High religious commitm	55	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
33	Abhay Aryan	M.	21	Khagariya, Bihar	12	lower middle (III)	43	very High religious commitm	57	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
34	Aditya Subham	M.	18	Delhi	16	upper-middle (II)	30	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
35	Vidya Biswas	F.	19	New Delhi	16	upper-middle (II)	15	low religious commitment	36	below average wellbeing	27	moderate community Integration
36	Lavanya Bhatnagar	F.	19	Sonapat	20	Upper middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	52	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
37	Sonia Rani	F.	49	Sirmaur, Himachal Pradesh	16	Upper middle (II)	50	very High religious commitm	60	very High mental well-being	48	High community Integration
38	_	F.	20	Delhi	25	Upper middle class (II)	24	moderate religious commitm	56	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
39	Jayesh	M.	26	Bhubaneswar, Odisha	11	lower middle (III)	33	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
40	Pankaj Kumar	M.	19	Bihar	21	upper middle (II)	28	moderate religious commitm	34	below average wellbeing	38	High community Integration
41	Rishi Pal	M.	19	Kanpur, UP	8	upper lower(IV)	34	High religious commitment	51	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
42	_	F.	30	Delhi	26	upper (I)	38	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	32	moderate community Integration
43	Sudha	F.	49	Delhi	28	upper (I)	31	High religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	42	High community Integration
44	H. Risha	M.	18	UP	18	upper-middle class (II)	42	Very High religious commitm	49	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
45	_	F.	22	Mumbai	25	upper middle class (II)	44	very High religious commitm	53	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
46	Vijay Pratap Singh	M.	21	Prayagraj	27	upper(I)	42	very High religious commitm	58	average to high wellbeing	43	High community Integration
47	Vivek Patel	M.	35	Varanasi	26	upper(I)	20	moderate religious commitm	56	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
48	-	M.	26	Bengaluru	28	upper(I)	26	moderate religious commitm	40	below average wellbeing	36	High community Integration
49	Aditya Rajawat	M.	21	Jaipur	27	upper(I)	44	very High religious commitm	62	very High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
50	Madhu Singh	F.	44	New Delhi	27	upper(I)	29	moderate religious commitm	50	average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
51	Avi	M.	30	Mumbai	27	upper (I)	12	low religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
52	Yashika	F.	18	Delhi	14	lowe middle (III)	30	High religious commitment	43	average to high wellbeing	32	Moderate community Integration
53	Shashank Shekhar Pr	M.	30	Prayagraj	23	upper middle (II)	15	low religious commitment	44	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
54	Arnimma Bansal	F.	18	New Delhi	18	upper-middle (II)	23	moderate religious commitm	39	below average wellbeing	32	moderate community Integration
55	Pratima	F.	44	New Delhi	26	upper (I)	36	High religious commitment	56	High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
56	Himang Gautam	M.	19	New Delhi	25	upper middle (II)	30	High religious commitment	38	below average wellbeing	26	moderate community Integration
57	Rahul Yadav	M.	22	Ghaziabad	4	lower (V)	29	moderate religious commitm	56	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
58	Mihir	M.	22	New Delhi	13	lower middle (III)	24	moderate religious commitm	52	average to high wellbeing	42	High community Integration
59	Aditi Gupta	F.	21	New Delhi	22	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	48	average to high wellbeing	33	moderate community Integration
60	_	M.	20	Noida	21	upper middle (II)	22	moderate religious commitm	50	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
61	Pankaj Kumar Srivast	M.	51	Prayagraj	17	upper middle (II)	50	very High religious commitm	70	High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
62	Mradul Nanda	M.	20	Etawah	27	upper (I)	19	low religious commitment	40	below average wellbeing	37	High community Integration
63	_	F.	19	Indrapuram, Ghaziabad	25	upper middle (II)	28	moderate religious commitm	52	average to high wellbeing	32	moderate community Integration
64	_	F.	20	Delhi	27	upper (I)	21	moderate religious commitm	52	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
65	Sajal pratap singh	M.	20	Karnal, Haryana	28	upper (I)	26	High religious commitment	61	very high mental well-being	34	moderate community Integration
66	Abhay Singh Yadav	M.	47	Chandauli	17	upper middle (II)	41	very High religious commitm	55	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
67	Riya	F.	23	Jaipur	21	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	48	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
68	_	M.	34	Chandauli	9	upper lower (IV)	10	low religious commitment	42	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
69	Prakash Chand Jat	M.	32	Jaipur	4	lower (V)	47	Very High religious commitm	55	average to high wellbeing	44	High community Integration
70	Sangita	F.	30	Bihar	5	uper lower (IV)	25	moderate religious commitm	54	average to high wellbeing	49	High community Integration
71	Priya Singh	F.	33	Pune	27	upper (I)	13	Low religious commitment	41	average to high wellbeing	28	Moderate community Integration
72	Ravindra	M.	19	Chitrakoot, UP	10	upper lower (IV)	34	High religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
73	Keshav Dixit	M.	18	Sirmaur, Himachal Pradesh	21	upper middle (II)	36	High religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
74	Adhrav Shah	M.	32	New Delhi	21	upper middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
75	Chauhan Meena	F.	46	Jaipur	19	upper middle (II)	47	Very High religious commitm	63	Very High mental well-being	41	High community Integration
76	Nelabh Nigam	M.	27	UP	27	upper (I)	50	Very High religious commitm	70	Very High mental well-being	47	High community Integration
77	Prerna Verma	F.	49	Delhi	19	upper middle (II)	31	High religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	33	moderate community Integration
78	Sarika Singh	F.	46	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	24	moderate religious commitm	65	Very High mental well-being	40	High community Integration
79	Amarendar Yadav	M.	39	Chandauli, UP	20	upper middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
80	Rajendra Singh	M.	50	Jaipur	28	upper (I)	47	Very High religious commitm	53	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
81	_	F.	39	Jaipur	28	upper (I)	50	Very High religious commitm	56	average to high wellbeing	28	moderate community Integration
82	Nitish yadav	M.	30	Chandauli UP	28	upper (I)	23	moderate religious commitm	38	below average wellbeing	47	High community Integration
83	Piyush Pant	M.	22	Dehradun	28	upper (I)	39	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	46	High community Integration
84	Anurag Yadav	M.	20	Varanasi	25	upper middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	64	Very High mental well-being	41	High community Integration
85	_	M.	36	Lucknow	28	upper (I)	37	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	44	High community Integration
86	Mayank Savita	M.	21	Darshanpurva, Kanpur	17	upper middle (II)	40	High religious commitment	53	average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
87	Beena Yadav	F.	38	Chandauli UP	20	upper middle (II)	34	High religious commitment	53	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
88	Alok	M.	20	Kanpur	22	upper middle (II)	35	High religious commitment	53	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration high
89	Sunny Kumar	M.	25	Siwan, Bihar	19	upper-middle (II)	50	High religious commitment	70	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration high
90	Ajay	M.	26	Pune	27	upper (I)	29	moderate religious commitm	69	average to high wellbeing	31	moderate community Integration
91	Ankit	M.	35	Prayagraj	25	upper-middle (II)	28	moderate religious commitm	37	below average wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
92	Ankur Singh	M.	33	Banda	21	upper-middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	55	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
93	Ujjwal Shrivastava	M.	34	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	29	moderate religious commitm	42	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration

94	Sadhana Pandit	F.	50	Delhi	25	upper-middle (II)	22	moderate religious commitm	57	average to high wellbeing	31	moderate community Integration
95	Rishab Pandey	M.	18	Kanpur, UP	10	upper lower (IV)	42	High religious commitment	55	average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
96	Avinash Yadav	M.	14	Chandauli, UP	20	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	76	average to high wellbeing	57	High community Integration
97	Anurag Yadav	M.	17	Chandauli, UP	20	upper middle (II)	40	Very High religious commitment	61	Very High mental well-being	41	High community Integration
98	Shivam	M.	35	Lucknow	25	upper-middle (II)	27	moderate religious commitment	27	low mental well-being	37	High community Integration
99	_	F.	21	Jharkhand	8	upper lower (IV)	28	moderate religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
100	Rahul	M.	36	Bangalore	28	upper (I)	22	moderate religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
101	Jhanvi Kesarwani	F.	19	Prayagraj	19	upper middle (II)	19	low religious commitment	39	below average wellbeing	20	moderate community Integration
102	Tanmay Singh	M.	20	Delhi	23	upper middle (II)	31	High religious commitment	55	average to high wellbeing	36	High community Integration
103	Pragati Pandey	F.	22	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	32	High religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	39	High community Integration
104	Vaibhav Pandey	M.	29	Noida	17	upper-middle (II)	19	low religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
105	Arpita Pandey	F.	35	Prayagraj	29	upper (I)	31	High religious commitment	60	Very High mental well-being	45	High community Integration
106	Devesh Narain Mishr	M.	20	New Delhi	29	upper (I)	33	High religious commitment	46	average to high wellbeing	29	moderate community Integration
107	Neelesh Mishra	M.	18	New Delhi	21	upper middle (II)	24	moderate religious commitm	46	average to high wellbeing	35	High community Integration
108	Kaavya Gupta	F.	18	Kanpur	27	Upper (I)	37	High religious commitment	39	below average wellbeing	43	High community Integration
109	Ansh Tripathi	F.	20	Kapur	18	upper middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	48	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
110	Anshuman	M.	20	Kanpur	27	Upper (I)	30	High religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
111	Sunny Arora	M.	40	Sonapat, Haryana	22	upper middle (II)	25	moderate religious commitment	52	average to high wellbeing	39	High community Integration
112	Debashish Dutta	M.	42	Gurgaon, Haryana	28	upper (I)	34	High community Integration	62	very High mental well-being	43	High community Integration
113	Harsh Raj	M.	19	Mothari, Bihar	23	upper middle (II)	31	High religious commitment	60	Very High mental well-being	46	High community Integration
114	Shivam Vidua	M.	21	Tikamgarh, Madhya Pradesh	9	upper lower (IV)	19	low religious commitment	70	very High mental well-being	47	High community Integration
115	Ashumendra Chaudh	M.	21	Ayodhya	14	lower middle (III)	28	moderate religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
116	_	M.	20	Jhanjharpur	7	upper lower (IV)	46	Very High religious commitment	55	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
117	Bal Krishna Tiwari	M.	48	Ludhiana	13	lower Middle (III)	39	High religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	48	High community Integration
118	_	F.	22	New Delhi	24	upper middle (II)	11	low religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	34	Moderate community Integration
119	Anju Singh	F.	55	Lucknow	7	upper lower (IV)	38	High religious commitment	57	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
120	Saurav	M.	21	Chandauli	10	upper lower (IV)	17	low religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
121	Himanshu Singh	M.	19	Chandauli	21	upper middle (II)	30	High religious commitment	52	average to high wellbeing	24	moderate community Integration
122	Shashwat Kumar Sin	M.	22	Varanasi	20	upper middle (II)	36	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
123	Priyanshu Jaisawal	M.	22	Varanasi	17	upper middle (II)	41	Very High religious commitment	46	average to high wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
124	Ajay Pratap Singh	M.	59	Prayagraj	27	upper-middle (II)	39	High religious commitment	71	Very High mental well-being	47	High community Integration
125	_	M.	21	Prayagraj	15	lower middle (III)	10	low religious commitment	24	low mental well-being	30	moderate community Integration
126	Pranjal Singh	M.	20	Bangalore	7	upper lower (IV)	21	moderate religious commitment	43	average to high wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
127	Renu Singh	F.	37	Prayagraj	17	upper-middle (II)	50	Very High religious commitm	67	Very High mental well-being	40	High community Integration
128	_	F.	35	Bengaluru	22	upper middle (II)	10	low religious commitment	40	below average wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
129	_	F.	41	Pune	19	upper middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	51	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
130	Deepika Singh	F.	38	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	39	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	39	High community Integration
131	Niti Singh	F.	32	Uttar Pradesh	22	upper-middle (II)	23	moderate religious commitment	39	below average wellbeing	39	High community Integration
132	Mridul Srivastava	F.	34	Prayagraj	27	upper (I)	41	Very High religious commitm	66	very High mental well-being	51	High community Integration
133	Rekha Singh	F.	47	Mumbai	25	upper middle (II)	43	very High religious commitm	52	average to high wellbeing	38	High community Integration
134	Kajal Agarwal	F.	30	Odisha	25	upper middle (II)	22	moderate religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
135	Mrigank	M.	19	Chunar	21	upper middle (II)	50	Very High religious commitm	63	very High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
136	Abha Srivastava	F.	48	Prayagraj	27	upper (I)	40	Very High religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	44	High community Integration
137	Kalpna Sharma	F.	59	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	29	moderate religious commitment	60	very High mental well-being	38	High community Integration
138	Neel	M.	59	Prayagraj	9	upper lower (IV)	47	Very High religious commitment	70	Very High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
139	Anuj	M.	27	Corakhpur	18	upper middle (II)	33	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	10	low community Integration
140	_	M.	27	Bangalore	21	upper middle (II)	29	moderate religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
141	Sumk	M.	26	Prayagraj	25	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	48	High community Integration
142	Lata Singh	F.	55	UP	26	upper(I)	50	very High religious commitment	70	very High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
143	_	M.	22	New Delhi	20	upper-middle (II)	23	moderate religious commitment	48	average to high wellbeing	33	High community Integration
144	Aarti Varma	F.	44	UP	11	lower middle (III)	50	Very High religious commitment	65	Very High religious commit	50	High community Integration
145	Aaryan Gupta	M.	18	Haldwani, Uttarakhand	9	upper lower (IV)	29	moderate religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	44	High community Integration
146	Reshmi Saini	F.	39	Jaipur	25	upper middle (II)	44	Very High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
147	Vinod Kanwar	F.	46	Jaipur	20	upper middle (II)	31	High religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	44	High community Integration
148	Manan Bhatt	M.	20	Ghaziabad	23	upper middle (II)	28	moderate religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	47	High community Integration
149	_	F.	49	Pune	28	upper (I)	30	High religious commitment	46	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
150	Rishi Tandon	M.	51	Thane	29	upper (I)	35	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
151	Rakesh Moni	M.	54	Pune	29	upper (I)	21	moderate religious commitment	48	average to high wellbeing	33	moderate community Integration
152	_	M.	58	Odisha	27	upper (I)	39	High religious commitment	63	Very High mental well-being	49	High community Integration
153	Shivanshi	F.	15	Prayagraj	25	upper-middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	58	average to high wellbeing	31	moderate community Integration
154	_	F.	20	Prayagraj	23	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	59	average to high wellbeing	43	High community Integration
155	Shardul	M.	52	Pune	27	upper (I)	21	moderate religious commitment	53	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
156	Garima	M.	20	Haldia, W. Bengal	17	upper-middle (II)	41	very High religious commitment	60	Very High mental well-being	47	High community Integration
157	Sneha Bid	F.	21	Dhanbad	19	upper middle (II)	35	High religious commitment	60	Very High mental well-being	45	High community Integration
158	_	F.	21	Prayagraj	25	upper middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	43	High community Integration
159	Richa Tripathi	F.	20	Prayagraj	22	upper middle (II)	44	very High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
160	Chanderbhan	M.	47	Delhi	21	upper middle (II)	34	High religious commitment	34	below average wellbeing	38	High community Integration
161	_	F.	52	Maharashtra	29	upper (I)	36	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	39	High community Integration
162	Anand Kanwar	F.	22	Jaipur	24	upper middle (II)	31	High religious commitment	40	below average wellbeing	33	moderate community Integration
163	Sandy	M.	21	Shillong, Meghalaya	14	lower middle (III)	25	moderate religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	27	moderate community Integration
164	Saumik	M.	20	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	33	High religious commitment	42	average to high wellbeing	41	High community Integration
165	_	F.	19	Gurgaon	28	upper (I)	23	moderate religious commitment	32	below average wellbeing	34	moderate community Integration
166	Gaurav Singh	M.	20	New Delhi	6	upper lower (IV)	38	High religious commitment	54	Average to high wellbeing	42	High community Integration
167	Seema	F.	50	Delhi	23	upper middle (II)	34	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	32	moderate community Integration
168	Mukesh Chaudhary	M.	26	Mathura	16	upper middle (II)	33	High religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
169	Kaushal	F.	19	Delhi	28	upper (I)	29	moderate religious commitment	46	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
170	Lovish	M.	21	Delhi	13	lower middle (III)	35	High religious commitment	50	average to high wellbeing	37	High community Integration
171	_	M.	55	Odisha	26	upper (I)	44	Very High religious commitment	64	Very High mental well-being	42	High community Integration
172	_	F.	53	Odisha	14	lower middle (III)	44	Very High religious commitment	57	average to high wellbeing	45	High community Integration
173	Swati Srivastava	F.	34	Prayagraj	25	upper-middle (II)	49	Very High religious commitment	66	very High mental well-being	48	High community Integration
174	_	F.	34	Prayagraj	28	upper (I)	25	moderate religious commitment	43	average to high wellbeing	29	moderate community Integration
175	Srijan Tiwari	M.	24	Prayagraj	21	upper middle (II)	35	High religious commitment	56	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
176	_	F.	29	Allahabad	12	lowe middle (III)	36	High religious commitment	60	Very High mental well-being	40	High community Integration
177	Aditi	F.	19	UP	19	upper middle (II)	11	low religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	30	moderate community Integration
178	Shriya	F.	22	Allahabad	14	lower middle (III)	16	low religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	27	moderate community Integration
179	Amit Rai	M.	34	Lucknow	25	upper middle (II)	37	High religious commitment	54	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
180	Anshu Nath	F.	21	Prayagraj	10	upper lower (IV)	15	low religious commitment	38	below average wellbeing	20	moderate community Integration
181	Kritika Tripathi	F.	18	Chakia, Prayagraj	20	upper middle (II)	32	High religious commitment	46	average to high wellbeing	43	High community Integration
182	_	F.	23	Prayagraj	25	upper middle (II)	18	low religious commitment	47	average to high wellbeing	33	moderate community Integration
183	Jyoti Mukherjee	F.	33	Prayagraj	29	upper (I)	45	Very High religious commitment	61	Very High mental well-being	50	High community Integration
184	Sweta Singh	F.	34	Prayagraj	18	upper middle (II)	38	High religious commitment	49	average to high wellbeing	31	moderate community Integration
185	Anand Kumar Pandey	M.	54	Prayagraj	18	upper middle (II)	26	moderate religious commitment	43	average to high wellbeing	50	High community Integration
186	Ajay Dubey	M.	49	Prayagraj	23	upper middle (II)	20	moderate religious commitment	42	average to high wellbeing	40	High community Integration
187	Pradeep Singh Seng	M.	54	Prayagraj	20	upper middle (II)	24	moderate religious commitment	57	average to high wellbeing	49	High community Integration
188	_	F.	24	Prayagraj	25	upper middle (II)	24	moderate religious commitment	64	Very High mental well-being	48	High community t

percent

